

Article

Composition Identities of Chebyshev Polynomials, via 2×2 Matrix Powers

Primo Brandi ^{1,*} and Paolo Emilio Ricci ²

¹ Dipartimento di Matematica e Informatica, Università degli Studi di Perugia, Via Vanvitelli, 1, 06123 Perugia, Italy

² International Telematic University UniNettuno, Corso Vittorio Emanuele II, 39, 00186 Roma, Italy; paoloemilioricci@gmail.com

* Correspondence: primo.brandi@unipg.it

Received: 26 March 2020; Accepted: 14 April 2020; Published: 6 May 2020

Abstract: Starting from a representation formula for 2×2 non-singular complex matrices in terms of 2nd kind Chebyshev polynomials, a link is observed between the 1st kind Chebyshev polynomials and traces of matrix powers. Then, the standard composition of matrix powers is used in order to derive composition identities of 2nd and 1st kind Chebyshev polynomials. Before concluding the paper, the possibility to extend this procedure to the multivariate Chebyshev and Lucas polynomials is touched on.

Keywords: Chebyshev polynomials; matrix powers; composition identities

MSC: 33C45; 15A16

1. Introduction

To the authors' knowledge, very few composition identities for Chebyshev polynomials [1,2] are known, apart from the classical one for 1st kind: $T_m[T_n(x)] = T_{mn}(x)$, and others for the 2nd kind, published by Kimberling in [3].

Recently, some convolution equations or sums of finite products of Chebyshev polynomials appeared in literature [4,5], but none of the composition type.

This is the motivation of this article, which aims to fill a gap in the literature on a very well known topic [1,6], which concerns the polynomials of Chebyshev, one of the most used families of orthogonal polynomials.

In what follows, by using a known connection [7] of the 2nd kind Chebyshev polynomials with 2×2 matrix power representation, we derive in a straightforward way composition identities involving 1st and 2nd kind Chebyshev polynomials.

The key result is the useful remark that the trace of matrix powers are simply related to the 1st kind Chebyshev polynomials. Therefore, the standard composition of matrix powers implies the searched composition identities. The considered method could be theoretically used in order to find an infinite number of such compositions, but of course the relative formulas become more and more complicated as the number of nested powers is considered.

The obtained equations could obviously be derived even by using the trigonometric forms of Chebyshev polynomials, but the method proposed in this article seems to be more simple and efficient.

Before concluding the paper, it is mentioned that a similar approach could be used in order to construct composition identities for two variable Chebyshev polynomials and even for the so-called $F_{k,n}$ functions that are solutions of linear recurrence equations, with suitable initial conditions, which include the multivariate case of 2nd kind Lucas polynomials, and are useful in order to represent powers of higher order matrices.

2. On Powers of a 2×2 Non-Singular Matrix

Let $\mathcal{A} = \{a_{h,k}\}_{2 \times 2}$ be a non-singular complex matrix, and let

$$u_1 := \operatorname{tr} \mathcal{A}, \quad u_2 = \det \mathcal{A} \neq 0, \quad (1)$$

respectively the trace and the determinant of \mathcal{A} .

The characteristic equation is given by

$$\lambda^2 - u_1 \lambda + u_2 = 0, \quad (2)$$

and denote by λ_1 and λ_2 the eigenvalues of \mathcal{A} .

We start by considering two results connecting matrix powers with Chebyshev polynomials.

The first result is the representation theorem for matrix powers, proved in [7]:

Theorem 1. *The integer powers of \mathcal{A} , ($n \geq 2$), are given by:*

$$\mathcal{A}^n = u_2^{(n-1)/2} U_{n-1} \left(\frac{u_1}{2u_2^{1/2}} \right) \mathcal{A} - u_2^{n/2} U_{n-2} \left(\frac{u_1}{2u_2^{1/2}} \right) \mathcal{I}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{I} is the 2×2 identity matrix, and

$$U_0(x) = 1, \quad U_1(x) = 2x, \quad U_2(x) = 4x^2 - 1, \quad U_3(x) = 8x^3 - 4x, \dots \quad (4)$$

are the second kind Chebyshev polynomials.

In particular, we find:

$$\mathcal{A}^2 = u_2^{1/2} U_1 \left(\frac{u_1}{2u_2^{1/2}} \right) \mathcal{A} - u_2 U_0 \left(\frac{u_1}{2u_2^{1/2}} \right) \mathcal{I} = u_1 \mathcal{A} - u_2 \mathcal{I}, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathcal{A}^3 = u_2 U_2 \left(\frac{u_1}{2u_2^{1/2}} \right) \mathcal{A} - u_2^{3/2} U_1 \left(\frac{u_1}{2u_2^{1/2}} \right) \mathcal{I}, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathcal{A}^4 = u_2^{3/2} U_3 \left(\frac{u_1}{2u_2^{1/2}} \right) \mathcal{A} - u_2^2 U_2 \left(\frac{u_1}{2u_2^{1/2}} \right) \mathcal{I}, \quad (7)$$

We prove now the second result, which gives the trace of integer matrix powers \mathcal{A}^n ($n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) in terms of first kind Chebyshev polynomials $T_n(x)$:

$$T_0(x) = 1, \quad T_1(x) = x, \quad T_2(x) = 2x^2 - 1, \quad T_3(x) = 4x^3 - 3x, \dots \quad (8)$$

Theorem 2. *For any integer $n \geq 0$, it results:*

$$\operatorname{tr} \mathcal{A}^n = 2 u_2^{n/2} T_n \left(\frac{u_1}{2u_2^{1/2}} \right). \quad (9)$$

Proof. Since $\operatorname{tr} \mathcal{A}^n = t_1^n + t_2^n$, we find, in particular:

$$\operatorname{tr} \mathcal{A} = u_1, \quad \operatorname{tr} \mathcal{A}^2 = u_1^2 - 2u_2, \quad (10)$$

and by the Newton–Girard formulas, we can compute the following ones by the recursion:

$$\operatorname{tr} \mathcal{A}^n = u_1 (\operatorname{tr} \mathcal{A}^{n-1}) - u_2 (\operatorname{tr} \mathcal{A}^{n-2}), \quad (11)$$

which is the same recursion associated with Equation (2).

Putting

$$x = T_1(x) = u_1/2u_2^{1/2}, \quad (12)$$

so that $u_1 = 2u_2^{1/2}x$, and recalling the position (12), we find:

$$\text{tr } \mathcal{A} = 2u_2^{1/2}x = 2u_2^{1/2}T_1(x), \quad \text{tr } \mathcal{A}^2 = 4x^2u_2 - 2u_2 = 2u_2T_2(x). \quad (13)$$

Then, Equation (9) is true for $n = 1$ and $n = 2$. Therefore, Equation (9) holds for every $n \geq 0$, since the first and second member in this equation satisfy the same recursion (11) and initial conditions (13), (for $n = 0$ Equation (9) trivially holds). \square

Corollary 1. For any integer $n \geq 0$, assuming position (12), it results in:

$$\frac{\text{tr } \mathcal{A}^n}{2(\det \mathcal{A}^n)^{1/2}} = T_n(x), \quad (14)$$

and therefore the representation formula (3) becomes:

$$\mathcal{A}^n = u_2^{(n-1)/2}U_{n-1}(x)\mathcal{A} - u_2^{n/2}U_{n-2}(x)\mathcal{I}. \quad (15)$$

In particular, Equations (6) and (7), by using Equation (12), write:

$$\mathcal{A}^3 = u_2U_2(x)\mathcal{A} - u_2^{3/2}U_1(x)\mathcal{I}, \quad (16)$$

$$\mathcal{A}^4 = u_2^{3/2}U_3(x)\mathcal{A} - u_2^2U_2(x)\mathcal{I}, \quad (17)$$

3. Composition of Chebyshev Polynomials

3.1. A Preliminary Example

In this section, we prove some relations involving 1st and 2nd kind Chebyshev polynomials derived by matrix analysis.

Put by definition:

$$\mathcal{B} := \mathcal{A}^2 = u_1\mathcal{A} - u_2\mathcal{I}, \quad (18)$$

$$\mathcal{B}^2 = \mathcal{A}^4 = (u_1^2 - 2u_2)\mathcal{B} - u_2^2\mathcal{I},$$

that is:

$$\mathcal{A}^4 = (u_1^3 - 2u_1u_2)\mathcal{A} - (u_1^2u_2 - u_2^2)\mathcal{I}, \quad (19)$$

Note that

$$\text{tr } \mathcal{A}^2 = 2u_2T_2(x), \quad \det \mathcal{A}^2 = u_2^2 \neq 0, \quad (20)$$

$$\text{tr } \mathcal{B}^2 = 2u_2^2T_4(x), \quad \det \mathcal{B}^2 = u_2^4 \neq 0. \quad (21)$$

Then, we can prove the results:

Theorem 3. For any integer n , the following equations hold:

$$2x U_{n-1}[T_2(x)] = U_{2n-1}(x), \quad (22)$$

$$U_{2n-2}(x) = U_{n-1}[T_2(x)] + U_{n-2}[T_2(x)].$$

Theorem 4. For any integer n , the following equations hold:

$$U_{4n-1}(x) = U_{n-1}[T_4(x)] U_3(x),$$

$$U_{4n-2}(x) = U_{n-1}[T_4(x)] U_2(x) + U_{n-2}[T_4(x)], \quad (23)$$

$$2x U_{2n-1}[T_2(x)] = U_{n-1}[T_4(x)] U_3(x),$$

$$U_{2n-1}[T_2(x)] + U_{2n-2}[T_2(x)] = U_{n-1}[T_4(x)] U_2(x) + U_{n-2}[T_4(x)],$$

and, as a consequence of Equation (23), we find the identities:

$$U_{4n-1}(x) = 2x U_{2n-1}[T_2(x)], \quad (24)$$

$$U_{4n-2}(x) = U_{2n-1}[T_2(x)] + U_{2n-2}[T_2(x)],$$

which give back the recurrence relation for $U_n[T_2(x)]$.

Proof of Theorem 3.1. We compute the $2n$ th powers of \mathcal{A} in two different forms. By using Equations (3) and (18), and recalling the position (12), we find:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}^{2n} &= u_2^{(2n-1)/2} U_{2n-1} \left(\frac{u_1}{2u_2^{1/2}} \right) \mathcal{A} - u_2^n U_{2n-2} \left(\frac{u_1}{2u_2^{1/2}} \right) \mathcal{I} = \\ &= u_2^{(2n-1)/2} U_{2n-1}(x) \mathcal{A} - u_2^n U_{2n-2}(x) \mathcal{I}, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}^{2n} &= \mathcal{B}^n = u_2^{n-1} U_{n-1}[T_2(x)] \mathcal{B} - u_2^n U_{n-2}(T_2(x)) \mathcal{I} = \\ &= u_2^{n-1} U_{n-1}[T_2(x)] [u_1 \mathcal{A} - u_2 \mathcal{I}] - u_2^n U_{n-2}[T_2(x)] \mathcal{I} = \\ &= u_1 u_2^{n-1} U_{n-1}[T_2(x)] \mathcal{A} - u_2^n \{U_{n-1}[T_2(x)] + U_{n-2}[T_2(x)]\} \mathcal{I}. \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Comparing the coefficients of \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{I} in Equations (23) and (24), we find the two relations:

$$u_2^{(n-1)/2} U_{2n-1}(x) = u_1 u_2^{n-1} U_{n-1}[T_2(x)], \quad (27)$$

$$U_{2n-2}(x) = U_{n-1}[T_2(x)] + U_{n-2}[T_2(x)],$$

that is, our result, taking into account definition (12). \square

Proof of Theorem 3.2. Compute the $(4n)$ th power of \mathcal{A} in the following forms:

$$\mathcal{A}^{4n} = \left(\mathcal{A}^4 \right)^n = \mathcal{B}^{2n}. \quad (28)$$

We find:

$$\mathcal{A}^{4n} = u_2^{(4n-1)/2} U_{4n-1}(x) \mathcal{A} - u_2^{2n} U_{4n-2}(x) \mathcal{I}, \tag{29}$$

$$(\mathcal{A}^4)^n = u_2^{2n-2} U_{n-1}[T_4(x)] \mathcal{A}^4 - u_2^{2n} U_{n-2}[T_4(x)] \mathcal{I},$$

and, recalling Equation (7), with the position (12), it results:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}^{4n} = (\mathcal{A}^4)^n &= u_2^{2n-1/2} U_{n-1}[T_4(x)] U_3(x) \mathcal{A} - \\ &u_2^{2n} \{U_{n-1}[T_4(x)] U_2(x) + U_{n-2}[T_4(x)]\} \mathcal{I}, \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

$$\mathcal{A}^{4n} = \mathcal{B}^{2n} = u_2^{2n-1} U_{2n-1}[T_2(x)] \mathcal{B} - u_2^{2n} U_{n-2}[T_2(x)] \mathcal{I},$$

and, recalling Equation (5), we find:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}^{4n} = \mathcal{B}^{2n} &= u_1 u_2^{2n-1} U_{2n-1}[T_2(x)] \mathcal{A} - \\ &u_2^{2n} \{U_{2n-1}[T_2(x)] + U_{2n-2}[T_2(x)]\} \mathcal{I}, \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

comparing separately the coefficients of \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{I} , in Equations (29)–(30) and (30)–(31), we find Equation (23). \square

3.2. A More General Case

We prove now a more general result.

Theorem 5. For any integers n and m , the following equations hold:

$$U_{mn-1}(x) = U_{n-1}[T_m(x)] U_{m-1}(x), \tag{32}$$

$$U_{mn-2}(x) = U_{n-1}[T_m(x)] U_{m-2}(x) + U_{n-2}[T_m(x)].$$

Proof of Theorem 3.3. We compute the (mn) th power of \mathcal{A} in different forms. By Equation (15), we have:

$$\mathcal{A}^{mn} = u_2^{(mn-1)/2} U_{mn-1}(x) \mathcal{A} - u_2^{mn/2} U_{mn-2}(x) \mathcal{I}, \tag{33}$$

but

$$\mathcal{A}^{mn} = (\mathcal{A}^m)^n. \tag{34}$$

We find:

$$\mathcal{A}^{mn} = (\mathcal{A}^m)^n = u_2^{m(n-1)/2} U_{n-1}[T_m(x)] \mathcal{A}^m - u_2^{mn/2} U_{n-2}[T_m(x)] \mathcal{I}, \tag{35}$$

where

$$\mathcal{A}^m = u_2^{(m-1)/2} U_{m-1}(x) \mathcal{A} - u_2^{m/2} U_{m-2}(x) \mathcal{I},$$

Then, we find:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}^{mn} &= u_2^{(mn-1)/2} U_{n-1}[T_m(x)] U_{m-1}(x) \mathcal{A} - \\ &u_2^{mn/2} \{ U_{n-1}[T_m(x)] U_{m-2}(x) + U_{n-2}[T_m(x)] \} \mathcal{I}. \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

Then, Equation (32) follows by comparing the coefficients of \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{I} in Equations (33) and (36). \square

Remark 1. Further extensions of the results of Theorem 3.3 can be obtained by considering the powers of matrix \mathcal{A} in the form:

$$\mathcal{A}^{n_1 n_2 n_3} = (\mathcal{A}^{n_1 n_2})^{n_3} = (\mathcal{A}^{n_1})^{n_2 n_3}. \tag{37}$$

An obvious extension is considering a higher number of powers, that is, $n_1 n_2 \cdots n_k$. A lot of possible identities can be found using the different form of powers, but the relative equations become more and more complicated as the number k increases.

Remark 2. It is possible to consider an application of the above results to the second kind two-variable Chebyshev polynomials $U_n^{(2)}(u, v)$ [8–10], defined by the recursion:

$$\begin{aligned} U_0^{(2)}(u, v) &= 0, \quad U_1^{(2)}(u, v) = 1, \quad U_2^{(2)}(u, v) = u, \\ U_n^{(2)}(u, v) &= u U_{n-1}^{(2)}(u, v) - v U_{n-2}^{(2)}(u, v) + U_{n-3}^{(2)}(u, v). \end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

In fact, denoting by $J_1 = \text{tr} \mathcal{A}$, $J_2, J_3 = \det \mathcal{A}$, the invariants of a non-singular 3×3 matrix \mathcal{A} , by using the Hamilton–Cayley theorem, in [11], it has been shown that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}^n &= U_{n-1}^{(2)}(u, v) J_3^{\frac{n-2}{3}} \mathcal{A}^2 + \left[-v U_{n-2}^{(2)}(u, v) + U_{n-3}^{(2)}(u, v) \right] J_3^{\frac{n-1}{3}} \mathcal{A} + \\ &+ U_{n-2}^{(2)}(u, v) J_3^{\frac{n}{3}} \mathcal{I}, \end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

where $u := J_1 J_3^{-1/3}$, $v := J_2 J_3^{-2/3}$.

Furthermore, in the same article [11], the following expression of $U_n^{(2)}(u, v)$ in terms of the 2nd kind Chebyshev polynomials $U_n(\cdot)$ has been proven:

$$U_n^{(2)}(u, v) = \frac{- (xy)^{(n+2)/2} U_n \left(\frac{x+y}{2\sqrt{xy}} \right) + (xy)^{(n+5)/2} U_{n-1} \left(\frac{x+y}{2\sqrt{xy}} \right) + (xy)^{-n+1}}{1 - xy(x+y) + (xy)^3}, \tag{40}$$

where the variables x, y are related to the u, v by means of the system:

$$\begin{cases} u = x + y + (xy)^{-1} \\ v = xy + (x + y)(xy)^{-1}. \end{cases} \tag{41}$$

Then, by using Equation (39), the powers of \mathcal{A} can be represented in terms of the second kind ordinary Chebyshev polynomials.

Therefore, the technique used in this article can be exploited in order to derive composition identities for the 2-variable Chebyshev polynomials $U_n(x, y)$.

8. Lidl, R.; Wells, C. Chebyshev polynomials in several variables. *J. Reine Angew. Math.* **1972**, *255*, 104–111.
9. Lidl, R. Tschebyscheffpolynome in mehreren variablen. *J. Reine Angew. Math.* **1975**, *273*, 178–198.
10. Ricci, P.E. I polinomi di Tchebycheff in più variabili. *Rend. Mater.* **1978**, *11*, 295–327.
11. Ricci, P.E. Sulle potenze di una matrice. *Rend. Mater.* **1976**, *9*, 179–194.
12. Bruschi, M.; Ricci, P.E. An explicit formula for $f(A)$ and the generating function of the generalized Lucas polynomials. *Siam J. Math. Anal.* **1982**, *13*, 162–165. [[CrossRef](#)]
13. Brandi, P.; Ricci, P.E. A note on Golden ratio and higher order Fibonacci sequences. *Turkish J. Anal. Number Theory* **2020**, *8*, in print.
14. Natalini, P. A “hard to die” series expansion and Lucas polynomials of the second kind. *Appl. Math.* **2015**, *6*, 1235–1240. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Natalini, P. Solution of linear dynamical systems using Lucas polynomials of the second kind. *Appl. Math.* **2016**, *7*, 616–628. [[CrossRef](#)]

© 2020 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).